

Trucks on plant field. Germany.
Photo: Unsplash

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems> >

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond> >

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Smart Farming for Food Security

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

24 January 2023 - **Ecosystems** < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>> // **Features** < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Views < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

< <https://revolve.media/contributors/danielle-kutka>>

Danielle Kutka < <https://revolve.media/contributors/danielle-kutka>>

Project Manager at REVOLVE

< <https://revolve.media/contributors/danielle-kutka>>

Danielle Kutka < <https://revolve.media/contributors/danielle-kutka>>

Project Manager at REVOLVE

< <https://revolve.media/contributors/daniel-de-la-puente>>

Daniel de la Puente < <https://revolve.media/contributors/daniel-de-la-puente>>

R&D Project Manager, CTIC-CITA

< <https://revolve.media/contributors/daniel-de-la-puente>>

Daniel de la Puente < <https://revolve.media/contributors/daniel-de-la-puente>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Digitalization can support a more sustainable, food-secure Europe.

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

The impacts on global food supply chains due to Russia's invasion of Ukraine have exacerbated an already unstable European agri-food sector that has suffered a series of industry losses and disruptions due to climate disasters and the COVID-19 pandemic.

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

In 2022, production costs for the European agri-food sector have soared, with high energy costs threatening the continuity of food, feed, and agri-food commodities causing companies to [halt production, lay off staff or go out of business altogether](https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/220907-Extraordinary-Energy-Council-9-9-Agri-Food-Chain-Final.pdf) < <https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/220907-Extraordinary-Energy-Council-9-9-Agri-Food-Chain-Final.pdf>>. Due to gas shortages, [European fertilizer plants have shut down](https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-10-02/as-the-fertilizer-crisis-bites-farmers-take-drastic-steps) < <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-10-02/as-the-fertilizer-crisis-bites-farmers-take-drastic-steps>> while sanctions between the EU and Russia have led to [fertilizer prices tripling from a year ago](https://www.npr.org/2022/09/28/1125525861/how-the-war-in-ukraine-is-affecting-the-worlds-supply-of-fertilizer) < <https://www.npr.org/2022/09/28/1125525861/how-the-war-in-ukraine-is-affecting-the-worlds-supply-of-fertilizer>>. In the context of these turbulent times, farmers are being forced to make difficult decisions with the long-term impacts on food security yet to be known. With inflation affecting the entire production chain, one certainty is that consumers will pay the price.

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Contributors/daniel-de-lante

R&D Project Manager, CTIC-CITA

Featured in

REVOLVE

QUARTERLY INSIGHTS INTO A CHANGING WORLD N°46 | Winter 2022/23

Wastewater Reuse in Egypt [»](#) Maritime Spatial Planning [»](#) Sustainable Mobility for All [»](#) Kenya's Textile Industry [»](#)

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

<https://revolve.media/magazine/issue-46-winter-2022-23>

Top 10 Topics

[Decarbonization](https://revolve.media/topics/decarbonization) < <https://revolve.media/topics/decarbonization>>

[Transition](https://revolve.media/topics/transition) < <https://revolve.media/topics/transition>>

[Europe](https://revolve.media/topics/europe) < <https://revolve.media/topics/europe>>

[Transformation](https://revolve.media/topics/transformation) < <https://revolve.media/topics/transformation>>

Peaches in hand. Photo: Bakhrom Tursunov, Unsplash

Seeking smarter solutions

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

sustainable production and consumption of food <
[Energy < https://revolve.media/energy >](https://revolve.media/energy)>

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129319>, smart farming

solutions are needed to reshape Europe's fragile supply chains into more resilient,

[Mobility < https://revolve.media/mobility >](https://revolve.media/mobility)

[Opinions < https://revolve.media/opinions >](https://revolve.media/opinions)

<https://revolve.media/>

[Features < https://revolve.media/features >](https://revolve.media/features)

[Climate Action <](#)

Supply chain issues have pushed global food prices up by 56% when compared to
[Water < https://revolve.media/water >](https://revolve.media/water) the end of 2019 <
[https://www.allianz-trade.com/en_global/economic-](https://www.allianz-trade.com/en_global/economic-research/sector-reports/agrifood.html#link_internal_2)

[research/sector-reports/agrifood.html#link_internal_2](https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129319)>. The intelligent agriculture

[Circular < https://revolve.media/circular >](https://revolve.media/circular) in 2021 to €2.5 billion <
<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129319>>, however, in the

context of today's geopolitical situation, the actual growth could be lower. We need to
 seek smart solutions to overcome the multitude of crises being faced. One example is

the benefit that precision farming offers due to fertilizer shortages by [deploying](#)

[sensors to detect individual plant nutrient needs, cutting down on overall fertilizer use < https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2022-10-02/as-the-fertilizer-crisis-bites-farmers-take-drastic-steps >](#). Yet this is just the tip of the iceberg.

[Interviews < https://revolve.media/interviews >](https://revolve.media/interviews)

[opics/climate-action >](#)

[VIEWS < https://revolve.media/views >](https://revolve.media/views)

[cities <](#)

<https://revolve.media/>

[Events < https://revolve.media/events >](https://revolve.media/events)

[cities >](#)

[Circularity <](#)

<https://revolve.media/>

[opics/circularity >](#)

[Renewables <](#)

<https://revolve.media/>

[opics/renewables >](#)

[Transport <](#)

<https://revolve.media/>

[opics/transport >](#)

More topics... <

[https://revolve.media/topics-](https://revolve.media/topics-list/)
[list/>](#)

[Ecosystems < https://revolve.media/ecosystems >](https://revolve.media/ecosystems)

[Beyond < https://revolve.media/beyond >](https://revolve.media/beyond)

**Join Planet
REVOLVE today**

We strive to
communicate
sustainability for a better
world for the next

Support us by becoming
a member of REVOLVE
Planet today.

Become a
Member <
<https://planet.revolve.media>>

Stay up to date:

TECHNOLOGY SNAPSHOT
Digital Hams and Peaches

Using mathematical equations, CTIC CITA is creating virtual replicas of physical and chemical transformation of raw material to final product. Each processing step, from the salting, drying and curing of the meat, to the ripening of peaches before

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

The growing influx of digital solutions for agriculture will continue to take a leading role

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

but what may be most compelling is the potential that the combination of technologies can have on building resilient supply chains and food systems. It may seem unrealistic

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

war can have, yet a novel combination of cutting-edge technologies for two agri-food

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

Through the BBTWINS project, a group of innovative SMEs, research institutes, and

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Views < <https://revolve.media/views>>

blockchain, artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data to simulate entire value

chains from crop to final product. The project is producing digital

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

cases – Portesa, an integrated pork producer in Spain that grows its own feed for their pig and meat processing facilities, and Dimitra, a fruit cooperative in Greece.

Using machine learning components to replace parts of the logistics optimization

system, the project is working to [reduce the needed raw materials \(food, supplies,](https://bbtwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1_BBTWINS_Use-Case-Specifications-Descriptions.pdf)

[feedstock\) and cut transportation costs of agri-food production](https://bbtwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1_BBTWINS_Use-Case-Specifications-Descriptions.pdf) <

https://bbtwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1_BBTWINS_Use-Case-Specifications-Descriptions.pdf . It is also validating new products from the

valorization of waste streams for bio-processing that can be reused in agri-food

applications, including biofertilizers, which could serve as [alternatives to synthetic](https://research.rabobank.com/far/en/sectors/farm-inputs/the-russia-ukraine-war-impact-on-global-fertilizer-markets.html#:~:text=Agricultural%20commodity%20prices%20were%20high,4%25%20in%20the%20second%20year.>)

[fertilizers](https://research.rabobank.com/far/en/sectors/farm-inputs/the-russia-ukraine-war-impact-on-global-fertilizer-markets.html#:~:text=Agricultural%20commodity%20prices%20were%20high,4%25%20in%20the%20second%20year.>) < [https://research.rabobank.com/far/en/sectors/farm-inputs/the-russia-ukraine-war-impact-on-global-fertilizer-](https://research.rabobank.com/far/en/sectors/farm-inputs/the-russia-ukraine-war-impact-on-global-fertilizer-markets.html#:~:text=Agricultural%20commodity%20prices%20were%20high,4%25%20in%20the%20second%20year.>)

[markets.html#:~:text=Agricultural%20commodity%20prices%20were%20high,4%25%20in%20the%20second%20year.>](https://research.rabobank.com/far/en/sectors/farm-inputs/the-russia-ukraine-war-impact-on-global-fertilizer-markets.html#:~:text=Agricultural%20commodity%20prices%20were%20high,4%25%20in%20the%20second%20year.>) . Additional bio-based products include

nutraceuticals and protein concentrates for feed, that in addition to providing new

revenue streams for farmers and food producers could also be fed back into their

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Ecosystems Restoration

Sign up <
<https://revolve.media/join>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Pile of trash bins in Germany. Photo: Jasmin Sessler, Unsplash

Addressing consumer interests

In the wake of the pandemic, [52% of global consumers found that sustainability became more important to them](https://www.gfk.com/products/gfk-sustainability-) < <https://www.gfk.com/products/gfk-sustainability->

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

<https://www2.deloitte.com/uk/en/pages/consumer-business/articles/sustainable-consumer.html>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>> **Opinions** < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

While initiation and supply chain disruptions impact their purchasing power, the conscious consumer wants to know where their food comes from to address

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Based on blockchain, the BBTWINS digital platform uses an integrated traceability

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>> **Interviews** < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

system that allows producers to track and trace all material flows within their production chain. This also can inform consumers about the origin of the products they

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>> **Views** < <https://revolve.media/views>>

[processing plants and faster delivery times < https://bbtwins.eu/wp-](https://www.bbtwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1_BBTWINS_Use-Case-Specific)

[content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1 BBTWINS Use-Case-Specific](https://www.bbtwins.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/D6.1_BBTWINS_Use-Case-Specific)

Descriptions.pdf>. Using blockchain to ensure this traceability is pivotal for companies

with integrated production like Portesa, that see the value and advantages to having such transparent production chains.

Another consumer interest related to sustainability is the issue of food waste. More efficient and sustainable food production must address this issue, as the EU is committed to the [UN Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\)](https://sdgs.un.org/goals) <

<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>> that calls for the [halving of per capita global food waste at retail and consumer level by 2030](https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7734) <

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7734>, as well as the reduction of food losses along the food supply chain.

Despite being the world's [largest exporter of food and drink products](https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/resource/data-trends-of-the-european-food-and-drink-industry-2021/) <

<https://www.fooddrinkeurope.eu/resource/data-trends-of-the-european-food-and-drink-industry-2021/>>, a 2022 report found what has been dubbed the EU food waste

“scandal”: the [EU wastes more food than it imports](https://eeb.org/eu-wastes-) < <https://eeb.org/eu-wastes->

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7724 which was nearly double previous amounts due to better data of food waste on farms < [Energy < https://revolve.media/energy>](https://revolve.media/energy) [Opinions < https://revolve.media/opinions>](https://revolve.media/opinions)

<https://eeb.org/eu-wastes-more-food-than-it-imports-says-new-report/>. While

h [Mobility < https://revolve.media/mobility>](https://revolve.media/mobility) waste, improv [Features < https://revolve.media/features>](https://revolve.media/features)

production side through digitalization and the solutions offered by BBTWINS can

e [Water < https://revolve.media/water>](https://revolve.media/water) improvements in logistics [Interviews < https://revolve.media/interviews>](https://revolve.media/interviews) less food would go bad in transit, reducing the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions

associated with food consumption also at the consumer level.

[Circular < https://revolve.media/circular>](https://revolve.media/circular)

[VIEWS < https://revolve.media/views>](https://revolve.media/views)

TECHNOLOGY SNAPSHOT

[Events < https://revolve.media/events/>](https://revolve.media/events/)

Blockchain

Beyond cryptocurrencies – blockchain is a distributed database that stores a permanent and tamper-proof ledger of data. This distributed database is not controlled by a single entity, but the opposite – it is characterized by its decentralization, consensusbased mechanisms, smart contracts, and immutable records designed with security from its inception. Blockchain provides serializability, immutability and cryptographic verifiability without a single point of trust, unlike a standard database system. These properties have triggered blockchain adoption in a wide variety of industries beyond viral cryptocurrencies.

[Ecosystems < https://revolve.media/ecosystems>](https://revolve.media/ecosystems)

[Beyond < https://revolve.media/beyond>](https://revolve.media/beyond)

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Vegetables stall in market. Photo: PhotoMIX Company, Pexels

Skills for strong economies

A resilient food system should draw from the inextricable links between the agrifood industry and the bioeconomy, and the skills needed to ensure the uptake of smarter,

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

[Bioeconomy in Figures 2009-2019.pdf](#) shows the EU bioeconomy is stronger than ever, with a turnover of €2.4 trillion – the food and beverage sector accounting for half

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

this total. However, with this value [projected to reach €3 trillion by 2050 and three-](#)

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european->

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/long-term-vision-rural-areas/eu-rural-areas-numbers-en>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

to keep pace with the digital and green waves that will continue to shape the future of

the EU and its climate neutral ambitions. To ensure these transitions are taken up at

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/iews>>

at fosters and <https://bبتwins.eu/newsitem/digitalisation-key-to-rural-economies/> if the EU's

green transition [is to deliver an estimated 884,000 more jobs by](#)

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

<https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC129319> .

In October 2022, the European Commission announced 2023 as the [European Year of Skills](#) < <https://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=89&newsId=10431&furtherNews=yes> ; while dissolving the skills

gap is crucial to boosting innovation and competitiveness for the European economy,

digital skills are urgently needed. An estimated [70% of businesses consider a lack of](#)

[digitally skilled staff as an obstacle to investment, with nearly half of the EU](#)

[population having little to no level of digital skills](#) < <https://digital->

[strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-skills-and-jobs](https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-skills-and-jobs) .

In rural areas especially, where 30% of the EU population resides, [digital skills lag 14 percentage points behind](#)

[EU urbanites at 48% vs 62% respectively](#) <

[https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-](https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/long-term-vision-rural-areas/eu-rural-areas-numbers-en)

[democracy/long-term-vision-rural-areas/eu-rural-areas-numbers en](https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/new-push-european-democracy/long-term-vision-rural-areas/eu-rural-areas-numbers-en) .

Farming during these turbulent times is an opportunity to transform our food systems in

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

competitiveness of the European food ecosystem while also addressing consumer

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

needs and interests. The intimate link between agri-food and the bioeconomy should

be supported in this transition and should not be an afterthought, but rather at the core,

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

also support adequate skills development for a resilient and just European agrifood

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Read more

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

VIEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/iews>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

VIEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy> >

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility> >

Water < <https://revolve.media/water> >

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular> >

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems> >

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions> >

Features < <https://revolve.media/features> >

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews> >

VIEWS < <https://revolve.media/views> >

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/> >

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond> >

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

Share this article

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

A Future Worth Inheriting < <https://revolve.media/features/a-future-worth-inheriting>>

Features | 10 October 2019
By **Danielle Kutka**

Journey of Water: Remembering to Value Rivers, One Jog at a Time < <https://revolve.media/features/journey-of-water-remembering-to-value-rivers-one-jog-at-a-time>>

Features | 4 March 2021
By **Richard Lee**

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>
More about ecosystems

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

[ve.media/water](https://revolve.media/water)
Tar Sands II <
<https://revolve.media/features/tar-sands-2>>
[olve.media/circular](https://revolve.media/circular)
Features | 21 June 2013
By **Jenny Christensson**

revolve.media/towers>
Timber Towers
<https://revolve.media/views/timber-towers>>
[olve.media/events/](https://revolve.media/events/)>
VIEWS | 28 March 2023

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>
Events related to ecosystem restoration

Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

[ve.media/water](https://revolve.media/water)>
Cassandra
Conference 2023 <
[olve.media/circular](https://revolve.media/olve.media/circular)>
[https://revolve.media](https://revolve.media/events/cassandra-conference-2023)
[/events/cassandra-](https://revolve.media/events/cassandra-conference-2023)
[conference-2023](https://revolve.media/events/cassandra-conference-2023)>
Events | Online

[EURESFI, European](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience)
[Urban Resilience](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience)
Forum <
[https://revolve.media](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience-forum)
[/events/euresfi-](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience-forum)
[europeans/urban-](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience-forum)
[resilience-forum](https://revolve.media/urban-resilience-forum)>
Events | Cascais, Portugal

Social

Join us today!

Barcelona | Brussels | Lisbon | Madrid | Mumbai

Email...

Sign up

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>>

Beyond < <https://revolve.media/beyond>>

See the world from different vantage points
Perspective is everything and everything is changing.

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

media/> **Opinions** < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

[https://twitter.co](https://twitter.com/RevolveMediaCo)

[m/RevolveMediaC](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[o> in <](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[https://www.linke](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[din.com/compan](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[/revolve-](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[group/my](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[y/> @ <](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[https://ww](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[gram.com/revolve](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[media/> <](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[https://www.yout](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[ube.com/channel/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[UC7p4oHw7-](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[yf5Oh-R7qzOjKg?](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[view_as=subscrib](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[er> <](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[https://www.flick](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[r.com/photos/rev](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

[olve-group>](https://www.linkedin.com/company/revolve-group/my)

I agree to the [REVOLVE Privacy Policy < https://agency.revolve.media/privacy-policy/>](https://agency.revolve.media/privacy-policy/)

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

VIEWS < <https://revolve.media/views>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events>>

Ecosystems < <https://revolve.media/ecosystems>> **Terms & Conditions** < <https://agency.revolve.media/terms-conditions/>> **Privacy & Cookies** <

<https://agency.revolve.media/privacy-policy/>> **Other Policies** < <https://agency.revolve.media/sustainability>>

Energy < <https://revolve.media/energy>> | This website is run on 100% renewable energy
Opinions < <https://revolve.media/opinions>>

Mobility < <https://revolve.media/mobility>>

Features < <https://revolve.media/features>>

Water < <https://revolve.media/water>>

Interviews < <https://revolve.media/interviews>>

Circular < <https://revolve.media/circular>>

IEWS < <https://revolve.media/iews>>

Events < <https://revolve.media/events/>>